

DOI:

Development of foreign language communicative culture of students in the educational environment at university

Малик В. М., аспірант кафедри педагогіки, професійної освіти та управління освітніми закладами

*Вінницький державний педагогічний університет
імені Михайла Коцюбинського*

In today's conditions, the problem of forming a foreign language communicative culture of students in the context of international communication is of great importance among lecturers, sociologists, culturologists and psychologists around the world. Now academic mobility of students around the world has increased significantly and at the same time, there has been an increase in the number of foreign students, which indicates the intensive development of cooperation in education and defines as the most relevant and important area of higher education institutions in many countries. The development of interstate academic cooperation, which includes comprehensive, multicultural education and development of students, contributes to the spiritual rapprochement of people, international relations, the formation of a foreign language culture of international communication and leveling the world's borders.

A lot of higher education institutions in Ukraine have been training a large numbers of foreign students, cooperating with higher education institutions and enterprises in other countries, participating in student exchange programs. Due to these conditions the task of forming the foreign language communicative culture of students in the context of international communication is becoming increasingly important for higher education institutions of our country.

The process of globalization taking place in the modern world contributes to the expansion of cultural boundaries, affects the intensity of intercultural communication. The expansion of intercultural ties inevitably leads to new social, political, religious, economic and educational problems.

Scholars are convinced that foreign language communicative culture in international communication is one of the important aspects of basic personality culture, which should be considered a key component of culture, where foreign language culture itself serves as a system to improve professional and socially significant personality qualities, and a foreign language is a means of communication and the development of a foreign language communicative culture in the context of international communication.

Analysis of the structural components of a foreign language communicative culture in international communication, namely "culture", "language", "language personality" and "culture in international communication", shows that there is no unity in their understanding and not

always these and similar concepts are revealed quite accurately, but there are common functions that they perform for the development and formation of communicative abilities of the individual.

Kendzior P. argues that culture in its proper meaning can be seen not only as a material asset and spiritual values created by a person in the process of purposeful activity, but also primarily as a relationship that arises in the accumulation, exchange and transmission of foreign cultural meanings. The use of the activity approach in the educational process enriches it with new values and meanings that accumulate in various layers of the educational potential of culture.

If we talk about the development of foreign language culture, it is impossible without intercultural communication, where the cultural function is performed by the foreign language in which it is carried out and formed by a linguistic person who owns it, where this fact is confirmed by American linguist Sapir E. The scientist denying the biological definiteness of a foreign language, noting that language is a purely human, almost instinctive way of transmitting thoughts, emotions and desires, emphasizes the communicative function of language as an expressive form of communicative behavior.

So, the modern learning environment should be aimed at developing personal intellectual abilities, critical thinking skills, communication skills important for understanding cultural diversity, establishing contacts between representatives of different nationalities in economic, social and political spheres at different levels. Thus, the vital need to cultivate the foreign language culture of international communication is explained by the fact that the population of many countries and regions in its composition is multinational.